

**METHODOLOGY OF FORMING READING COMPREHENSION
SKILLS IN MOTHER LANGUAGE CLASSES OF PRIMARY CLASS**

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Abstract: This article talks about improving reading comprehension skills in the subject of the mother tongue, which is a new generation of textbooks for primary grades.

Key words: mother tongue, reading literacy, science, elementary school, literacy, lesson effectiveness.

Forming the knowledge and skills of schoolchildren, educating them in the spirit of loyalty to national and universal values, increasing the prestige of the teaching profession and the quality of pedagogues, improving textbooks and teaching methods based on the requirements of the times, bringing public educational institutions to international standards. in order to establish responsive modern models, as well as in accordance with the state program for the implementation of the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026 in the "Year of Human Dignity and Active Neighborhood" Decree No. PF-134 dated May 11 "On approval of the national program for the development of public education in 2022-2026" was approved. How well do elementary school graduates of Uzbekistan study compared to their peers in other countries, what is the level of reading literacy of Uzbek students, how is reading a hobby for 4th graders, family how it contributes to the development of literacy, how the process of teaching reading is organized in our country today, how the process of teaching reading in Uzbekistan compares to other countries Basic issues such as the

uniqueness, if so, how it manifests itself, the differences between the methods used by teachers of our primary classes and the methods used by teachers in other countries are studied. According to the 2016 PIRLS study, out of 50 countries, Russia, Singapore, Hong Kong, Ireland and Finland scored the highest, while Russian and Singaporean students scored the highest in reading and comprehension. showed the highest results. Also, Russian primary school students led the world in this criterion. Mother tongue and reading literacy education focuses on four language skills: reading comprehension, listening comprehension, speaking and writing, and grammatical literacy. In addition, the PIRLS international study can serve public policy in the field of education in improving reading and teaching, which allows for international comparison of data on the level of development of reading comprehension skills of primary school students. Reading comprehension is the ability to process text, understand its meaning, and relate it to what the reader already knows. To know the dictionary meaning of words, to know the contextual meaning of words, to understand the interconnection of blocks of text, to draw conclusions based on the fragments of the text, to determine the main idea of the text, to be able to answer the questions based on the text, to recognize and separate the tone of the artistic arts or phrases used in the text the ability to determine the mood of the situation (affirmation, denial, questioning, command), determine the author's purpose, intention and point of view, and draw conclusions about the author are the skills and abilities necessary for effective understanding of the read text. (discourse-semantics). The ability to read and understand a text is influenced by the above skills of the reader and the ability to process information. If the reader does not know the meaning of the word, he spends a lot of time processing the text, because he tries to understand the misunderstood words in the text individually, which also allows understanding. There are many exercises for the development of reading comprehension skills, including increasing vocabulary, critical analysis

of the text, skim reading. Listening comprehension is listening and understanding the speaker's speech from the radio, tape recorder, CD, and during communication. In some literature, it is also called auditory. It is a complex speech activity, because the listener needs to be able to quickly accept the form and keep it in memory, otherwise there is no source, conditions, means to be able to see it again, read it and understand it. Research shows that students' listening comprehension is less developed than speaking. A student receives six times more information by reading and seeing than by listening and understanding. The reason is that he has worked on it less, because of its complexity. Listening comprehension is an integral part of speaking. Listening comprehension and speaking constitute oral speech. The science of mother tongue and reading literacy from the new generation textbooks plays a very important role in preparing primary school students for International PIRLS studies from the 1st grade. It requires great responsibility and hard work from the teacher in the formation of reading comprehension, listening comprehension, speaking and writing skills, as well as grammatical literacy. The purpose of the mother tongue and reading literacy textbook is to bring students to the level where they can speak grammatically correctly and communicatively freely in various life situations. The real needs of the student in using the language (social communication, academic education) are taken into account and the necessary linguistic devices are given in different speech situations. First of all, to improve reading comprehension, listening comprehension, speaking and writing, and grammatical literacy of elementary school students, to read correctly, to increase vocabulary, to teach broad thinking, to improve speech, consciousness It is necessary to properly organize the lessons of mother tongue and reading literacy in learning a number of features. Teaching using information technology in mother tongue and reading literacy classes, as in other subjects, helps to improve the quality of education and increase students' interest in the lesson. It is not an

exaggeration to say that this is the current demand. The use of information technology tools in mother tongue and reading literacy classes has both educational and educational importance in increasing the effectiveness of education. For example, effective use of text, decorative presentations, videos, audios, music, and animations in lessons also affects the effectiveness of lessons. In conclusion, it is important now that the primary school teacher can give students the necessary knowledge and skills, with a deep understanding of the importance of the mother tongue and reading literacy textbooks for each student. Then the students will become individuals with high oral and written literacy, reading comprehension and listening comprehension skills in the future. In addition, PIRLS, one of the current international studies for 4th grades it also serves as an effective foundation for research preparation.

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